

Supplementary Material for “Multi-User MIMO-OFDM ISAC for Low-Altitude UAV with Zero Sensing Resource Allocation”

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I. CLOSED-FORM OPTIMAL BEAMFORMING FOR THE SEARCHING STAGE

In this section, we provide a closed-form solution to the following problem,

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{f}_{u,q}} \quad & \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2 \\ \text{s.t.} \quad & |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \geq r_1, \\ & |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \geq r_2. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Theorem 1: The optimal solution to problem (1) is

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* = \begin{cases} \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} e^{j\phi_1} \mathbf{g}_1, & \text{if } r_2 \leq \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1|, \\ \frac{r_2}{\|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2} e^{j\phi_2} \mathbf{g}_2, & \text{if } r_2 \geq \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1|, \\ \mathbf{G}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{r}^*, & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where the phases ϕ_1, ϕ_2 can be chosen arbitrarily, $\mathbf{G} \triangleq [\mathbf{g}_1 \ \mathbf{g}_2]$, $\mathbf{K} \triangleq \mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2 & \mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{g}_2 \\ \mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1 & \|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2 \end{bmatrix}$, $\mathbf{S} \triangleq \mathbf{K}^{-1} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{12}^* & S_{22} \end{bmatrix}$, $\varphi_2^* = \pi - \angle S_{12}$, and $\mathbf{r}^* \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} r_1 \\ r_2 e^{j\varphi_2^*} \end{bmatrix}$.

Proof: We first consider the case when $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$ are linearly dependent. Assume $\mathbf{g}_2 = \alpha \mathbf{g}_1$ with $\alpha \in \mathbb{C}$ and $\mathbf{g}_1 \neq \mathbf{0}$. Then the two constraints in (1) act along the same direction and reduce to $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \geq r_1$ and $|\alpha| |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \geq r_2$, i.e.,

$$|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \geq R \quad \text{with} \quad R \triangleq \max\left(r_1, \frac{r_2}{|\alpha|}\right). \quad (3)$$

By the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| \leq \|\mathbf{g}_1\| \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|$, hence every feasible point obeys $\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\| \geq R/\|\mathbf{g}_1\|$ and therefore $\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2 \geq R^2/\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2$. This lower bound is attainable by

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* = \frac{R}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} e^{j\phi} \mathbf{g}_1, \quad \phi \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (4)$$

Next, we consider the case where one of the constraints is redundant. Assume $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$ are linearly independent. If

$$r_2 \leq \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1|, \quad (5)$$

then the second constraint is implied by the first one. Taking

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* = \alpha \mathbf{g}_1, \quad \text{with} \quad |\alpha| = \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2}, \quad (6)$$

we have $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = r_1$ and

$$|\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = |\alpha| |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| = \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| \geq r_2. \quad (7)$$

By the Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, (6) also attains the minimum norm permitted by the first constraint, hence it solves (1). The optimal value is

$$\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*\|^2 = \frac{r_1^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2}. \quad (8)$$

Symmetrically, if

$$r_1 \leq \frac{r_2}{\|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{g}_2|, \quad (9)$$

then the first constraint is implied by the second one, and the minimum-norm feasible point is

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* = \beta \mathbf{g}_2, \quad |\beta| = \frac{r_2}{\|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2}, \quad \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*\|^2 = \frac{r_2^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2}. \quad (10)$$

In either redundant case, the phase of α or β can be chosen arbitrarily.

Next, we consider the general case where $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$ are linearly independent and the two constraints are non-redundant. We first propose the following lemma.

Lemma 1: When $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$ are linearly independent, $r_1 |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| < r_2 \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2$ and $r_2 |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{g}_2| < r_1 \|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2$, for the optimal solution $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*$ of problem (1), the constraints are tight, i.e., $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = r_1$ and $|\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = r_2$.

Proof: Please refer to Section II. ■

By Lemma 1, we enforce

$$\mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q} = \mathbf{r}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) \triangleq \begin{bmatrix} r_1 e^{j\varphi_1} \\ r_2 e^{j\varphi_2} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (11)$$

For fixed phases, the minimum-norm feasible vector is the orthogonal projection

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{G})^{-1} \mathbf{r}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2) = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{r}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2), \quad (12)$$

with squared norm

$$\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)\|^2 = \mathbf{r}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2)^H \mathbf{S}\mathbf{r}(\varphi_1, \varphi_2). \quad (13)$$

Writing $\mathbf{S} = \begin{bmatrix} S_{11} & S_{12} \\ S_{12}^* & S_{22} \end{bmatrix}$, setting $\varphi_1 = 0$, we obtain

$$\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}(0, \varphi_2)\|^2 = r_1^2 S_{11} + r_2^2 S_{22} + 2r_1 r_2 \text{Re}\{S_{12} e^{j\varphi_2}\}. \quad (14)$$

Choosing $\varphi_2^* = \pi - \angle S_{12}$ minimizes the real part and yields $\text{Re}\{S_{12} e^{j\varphi_2^*}\} = -|S_{12}|$. Thus, the optimal solution to problem (1) can be obtained as

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* &= \mathbf{G}\mathbf{S}\mathbf{r}^* = \mathbf{G}(\mathbf{G}^H \mathbf{G})^{-1} \mathbf{r}^*, \\ \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*\|^2 &= r_1^2 S_{11} + r_2^2 S_{22} - 2r_1 r_2 |S_{12}|. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

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II. PROOF OF LEMMA 1

First, we prove that at least one constraint is tight. For any feasible $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}$, let $c_1 \triangleq |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}|$, $c_2 \triangleq |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}|$, and $r \triangleq \max\{r_1/c_1, r_2/c_2\} \in (0, 1]$. Then $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{u,q} \triangleq r \mathbf{f}_{u,q}$ is feasible with $\|\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{u,q}\|^2 = r^2 \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2 \leq \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2$, and at least one constraint is tight at $\tilde{\mathbf{f}}_{u,q}$.

We next prove that for the optimal solution $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*$, both constraints are tight, i.e., the case with only one constraint being active is impossible. By symmetry, assume a minimizer $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}$ obeys $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| = r_1$ and $|\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| > r_2$. Let $\mathbf{P}_1 \triangleq \mathbf{g}_1 \mathbf{g}_1^H / \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2$ and decompose

$$\mathbf{f}_{u,q} = \alpha \mathbf{g}_1 + \mathbf{z}, \quad \mathbf{z} \triangleq (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{P}_1) \mathbf{f}_{u,q} \perp \mathbf{g}_1. \quad (16)$$

Then $|\alpha| \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2 = |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| = r_1$ and

$$\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2 = \frac{r_1^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} + \|\mathbf{z}\|^2. \quad (17)$$

Define $\mathbf{p} \triangleq (\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{P}_1) \mathbf{g}_2 \neq \mathbf{0}$ (by linear independence) and let $s \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1$, $c \triangleq \mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{z} = \mathbf{p}^H \mathbf{z}$, $y_2 \triangleq s + c = \mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}$. Thus $|y_2| > r_2$. By Cauchy–Schwarz inequality, $|c| = |\mathbf{p}^H \mathbf{z}| \leq \|\mathbf{p}\| \|\mathbf{z}\|$, and for any prescribed c ,

$$\min_{\mathbf{z} \perp \mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{p}^H \mathbf{z} = c} \|\mathbf{z}\| = \frac{|c|}{\|\mathbf{p}\|}, \text{ attained at } \mathbf{z} = \frac{c}{\|\mathbf{p}\|^2} \mathbf{p}. \quad (18)$$

Note that under the non-redundancy assumptions $r_1 |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| < r_2 \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2$ and $r_2 |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{g}_2| < r_1 \|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2$, we have for any feasible point with $|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}| = r_1$ that

$$|s| = |\alpha| |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| = \frac{r_1}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| < r_2. \quad (19)$$

Next we find a smaller $|c|$ that keeps feasibility. Among all $\tilde{c} \in \mathbb{C}$ satisfying $|s + \tilde{c}| = r_2$, the choice colinear with s minimizes $|\tilde{c}|$; in particular

$$c^* \triangleq r_2 e^{j\angle s} - s, \quad |c^*| = r_2 - |s|. \quad (20)$$

Together with $|y_2| > r_2$, this implies, by the reverse triangle inequality,

$$|c| = |y_2 - s| \geq |y_2| - |s| > r_2 - |s| = |c^*|. \quad (21)$$

Define

$$\mathbf{z}^* \triangleq \frac{c^*}{\|\mathbf{p}\|^2} \mathbf{p}, \quad \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^* \triangleq \alpha \mathbf{g}_1 + \mathbf{z}^*. \quad (22)$$

Then $\mathbf{z}^* \perp \mathbf{g}_1$ and $\mathbf{p}^H \mathbf{z}^* = c^*$, so

$$|\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = r_1, \quad |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*| = |s + c^*| = r_2, \quad (23)$$

i.e., $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*$ is feasible and both constraints are tight. Moreover, by (18) and $|c^*| < |c|$,

$$\|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}^*\|^2 = \frac{r_1^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} + \frac{|c^*|^2}{\|\mathbf{p}\|^2} < \frac{r_1^2}{\|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2} + \frac{|c|^2}{\|\mathbf{p}\|^2} \leq \|\mathbf{f}_{u,q}\|^2, \quad (24)$$

contradicting the minimality of $\mathbf{f}_{u,q}$. Hence the case with only one active constraint is impossible. By symmetry, when $\mathbf{g}_1, \mathbf{g}_2$ are linearly independent, $r_1 |\mathbf{g}_2^H \mathbf{g}_1| < r_2 \|\mathbf{g}_1\|^2$ and $r_2 |\mathbf{g}_1^H \mathbf{g}_2| < r_1 \|\mathbf{g}_2\|^2$, both constraints must be tight at any minimizer.

III. COMPUTATIONAL COMPLEXITY ANALYSIS FOR THE SENSING ALGORITHM

We summarize the per-stage and end-to-end sensing complexity as below.

For the spatial-domain denoising step, element-wise division costs $\mathcal{O}(MNPQ)$. Forming the delay–Doppler tensor by 2D FFTs costs $\mathcal{O}(MNPQ \log(PQ_b))$ for searching and $\mathcal{O}(MNPQ \log(PQ))$ for tracking, and thresholding adds $\mathcal{O}(MNPQ)$.

For angle sensing with 2D spatial smoothing and MUSIC, building the subarray covariances over $I \times J$ subarrays of size $M_{\text{sub}} \times N_{\text{sub}}$ costs $\mathcal{O}(IJPQ(M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^2)$, followed by an EVD of size $M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}}$, i.e., $\mathcal{O}((M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^3)$. Evaluating the MUSIC spectrum is quadratic in $M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}}$ per tested angle pair, and therefore scales linearly with the number of angle grid points used in practice.

For delay–Doppler sensing, the ZF receive beamforming is calculated for all K_A angles with $\mathcal{O}(MNK_A^2 + K_A^3)$. Forming \mathbf{Y}_{k_A} costs $\mathcal{O}(MNPQ)$ per angle. The periodogram (2D FFT) per angle costs $\mathcal{O}(PQ_b \log(PQ_b))$ for searching and $\mathcal{O}(PQ \log(PQ))$ for tracking. The element-wise divisions and amplitude estimates are $\mathcal{O}(PQ)$ per angle and are dominated by the FFT part.

Assuming K_A is small, the dominant end-to-end sensing complexity for the searching stage is

$$\mathcal{O}(MNPQ \log(PQ_b)) + \mathcal{O}(IJPQ(M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^2) + \mathcal{O}((M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^3), \quad (25)$$

and for the tracking stage,

$$\mathcal{O}(MNPQ \log(PQ)) + \mathcal{O}(IJPQ(M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^2) + \mathcal{O}((M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^3). \quad (26)$$

In typical settings, the dominant contributors are the covariance accumulation $\mathcal{O}(IJPQ(M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^2)$ and the EVD $\mathcal{O}((M_{\text{sub}}N_{\text{sub}})^3)$.